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science
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Making Proteins with AI: A Breakthrough and a Regulatory Test

Issue/Problem

A [Nature study](#) published on July 9, 2025 revealed that Australian researchers successfully used AI to design synthetic proteins that block nutrient uptake in antibiotic-resistant *E. coli*. This breakthrough places Australia [alongside China and the US](#) at the forefront of AI-driven therapeutic protein design. While promising faster and more affordable treatments, these advances also expose serious gaps in regulatory oversight for AI-generated biological agents.

Description of the Problem

Existing biosafety and pharmaceutical regulations were designed for traditional research methods: incremental, well-documented changes to known proteins that regulators can easily trace and assess for safety. [They are poorly equipped to handle today's AI systems](#), which can generate entirely new proteins in seconds through complex algorithms that offer little insight into how outputs are generated or what their effects might be. Additionally, regulation remains [fragmented across jurisdictions](#) and [largely reliant on voluntary compliance](#). The [June 2025 California AI Policy Report](#) warns that without stronger, coordinated safeguards, AI tools could soon allow non-experts to design harmful biological agents with irreversible consequences.

Results

To address these risks, the European Union adopted the [AI Act](#), the world's first binding legal framework for AI. It classifies healthcare-related AI systems as "high-risk" and starting in August 2027, these systems will be required to undergo independent audits, maintain detailed records of training data, implement comprehensive risk management plans, monitor post-market performance, and ensure human oversight. In contrast, the US has taken a deregulatory approach aimed at reducing barriers to innovation, formalized through [Executive Order 14179](#), signed in January 2025.

Lessons Learned

Without a clear regulatory framework, [Canada risks falling behind global AI leaders](#), despite its early lead with the world's first national AI plan in 2017. [To remain competitive](#), it must decide whether to align with the EU's strict regulatory model, follow the US's hands-off approach, or pursue a distinct policy that balances protection with innovation.